

PREVALENCE OF ECTO AND ENDOPARASITES ASSOCIATED WITH DOGS

BY

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NAS/BIO/19/3137

**BEING A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
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**SUPERVISED
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DECEMBER 2021

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I, Zanira Imam with the registration number NAS/BIO/19/3137 hereby certify that this research project report is my original work and has been submitted to the Department of Biology, Al-Qalam University Katsina as part of the requirement for the award of B.Sc. (Hons) Biology.

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DEDICATION

I dedicated this Research to Almighty Allah who gives me the strength and knowledge to write this report. I also dedicated this report to my beloved parents and husband for their support throughout my studies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My sincere gratitude and appreciation goes to almighty Allah for his guidance to write this research project report. I really thank my beloved parents and husband for the utmost support. My brothers and sisters deserved my whole heart thanks as well.

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My special greeting goes to my daughter Fatima Zahra. May Almighty Allah guide her throughout her life Ameen?

I do recognize, with appreciation the great support and unrelenting encouragement with flowing ideas and educational and moral strategies from my supervisor Malam Abdullahi Shehu Ado who ensured the work has reached acceptable standard.

To all my lecturers, my friends, thank you all for your kind understanding and encouragement in my moments shared with you, your support makes my life worthy of experience.

ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to determine the prevalence of ectoparasites and endoparasites of dogs brought for treatment in the zonal Veterinary Clinic Kofar Kwaya Katsina state. To determine the prevalence of ectoparasites and endoparasites of dogs kept within and around Katsina. To relate the prevalence to sex, ages and species of the dogs. To identify the common species of parasites afflicting the animals in the area. The data to be collected was secondary data where the sample size depends on the available data. The variables to be examined were dogs affected by ectoparasite and endoparasite disease. Purposive sampling was used to access the data where a sample of 40 dogs taken with their age, sex-species type and the type of disease prevalence on either ecto or endoparasite disease. There is also the current lack of verified information on the dogs with serious disease. For these reasons dog owners should be reporting any disease they noticed from their dogs. Affected dogs need to be separated from unaffected ones to avoid being contacted with communicable disease. There is the need for health education to dog breeders and owners, vaccination of all stray dogs and proper use at least of acaricides and routine vermifuges. The emphasis should be put on alternative strategies for prevention because this measure aligns more with the overall principles of veterinary clinics, which is to maintain health rather than curing disease Future research in this area seems promising, there remain a lot of dogs to be studied but it is possible that there are some dogs that possess some disease that has a great side-effects.

The following component should be part of the abstract (brief information required here include):-

8

Background, which includes information about the problem (brief outline of the statement of the problem)

Purpose of the study (aim (s) and objective(s))

Methods

Results, summary of the study

Conclusion and implications of the study

There should be no citation of references in Abstract

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Dogs are the most successful canines, adapted to human habitation worldwide (Tannen, 2004). Recent genetic fossil and DNA evidence shows that dogs were as early as 100000 years ago (Lindblad, Wade, and Mikkelsen, 2005). They have contributed to the physical, the social and emotional well-being of their owners, particularly children where they are associated with a higher level of self-esteem (Robertson., Irwin, and Lymbery, 2000)] and have been used for hunting, as guards, draught animals, and for food (Swai, 2010). However, despite their beneficial effects, dogs remain a major threat to public health, as most of them harbour a bewildering number of infective stages of parasites transmissible to man and other domestic animals (Molyneux, 2004). Some of these parasites cause cutaneous and visceral larva migrans, mange, hydatidosis and tungiasis (Adamu Ali, and Adamu, 2011).

Parasites are eukaryotic, unicellular or multicellular, heterospecific organisms that derive nourishment by feeding on or within another organism (Adejoke, 2005). Parasitism is an association whereby the parasite is always benefiting while the other partner called the host of the parasitic association always suffers some degree of injuries that are capable of causing disease (Ogo *et al.*, 2005). Generally, parasites can be divided into two groups: endoparasites and ectoparasites. Endoparasites are parasites that live inside their host (Sasaki, Omobowale, and Tuzuk, 2007). Ectoparasites are parasites that live outside their host; they feed with at least part of their body outside the host epithelium (Sasaki *et al.*, 2007). Endo and ectoparasites can cause poor performance in animals and can lead to economic losses for the owner. Animal keepers must therefore understand the type of parasitism they encounter and the method of controlling them to

minimize losses (Bryson, Horak, and Hohn, 2000). Endoparasites such as gastrointestinal parasites are a common problem in dogs. Dogs become infected with the parasite either as they are born or later with their mother's milk. The microscopic examination of a stool sample will usually help to determine the presence of intestinal parasites. Gastrointestinal helminthiasis is the most commonly encountered disease in dogs and it also acts as a major constraint in dog keeping across the globe (Traub, Hobbs, & Adams, 2007; Saini, Ranjan, & Singla, 2012). Gastrointestinal helminthiasis in dogs may be asymptomatic or cause gastrointestinal disorders, lack of appetite, loss of weight, retarded growth and in severe cases death (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2014). The distribution and intensity of the disease are mainly influenced by geographical, climatic, cultural and economic factors (Robertson *et al.*, 2000). The level of hygienic conditions, lack of veterinary supervision and public awareness campaign concerning zoonotic diseases increase the transmission of the disease (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2014).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Dogs may be infected with pathogenic haemoparasites including *Babesia* species (Nalubamba, Hankanga, Mudenda, 2011; Eljadar, Singla, and Mustafa, 2012; Gonde, Chhabra, Singla, 2014); *Trypanosome* species (Keck *et al.*, 2009); *Leishmania*, *Hepatozoan*, *Ehrlichia*, *Anaplasma*, and *Dirofilaria* species which are transmitted through different arthropod vectors including ticks, lice, triatomines, mosquitoes, tabanids and phlebotomine sand flies (Kaure *et al.*, 2012). They cause an illness called Canine Vector-Borne Disease (CVBD) in tropical and subtropical countries, some of which are of zoonotic importance (Saritas *et al.*, 2005; Chhabra *et al.*, 2013). There is a paucity of information on the prevalence of endo and ectoparasites of dogs in the study area hence screening of dogs to detect parasitic infection is recommended to enable owners to institute treatment and to safeguard public health becomes imperative.

In urban and suburban areas, people traditionally raise dogs as pets. Health check-ups protect pets from infestation by ectoparasites. Thus, knowledge of types of species, density and prevalence of ectoparasites is needed to effectively control them (Scott, Miller, and Griffin,2001; Nuchjangreed and Somprasong,2007). Scarce information is available on the ectoparasites of dogs in the Shimoga region of Karnataka. So, the present work was undertaken to ascertain the actual status of ectoparasites infesting companion dogs of Katsina metropolis, Katsina.

Several epidemiological studies conducted in Nigeria and other parts of the world to assess the prevalence of parasite infections in canines have shown dogs to harbour ectoparasites such as *Sarcoptes* spp., *Ctenocephalides* spp., *Pulex irritans*, *Rhipicephalus sanguineus* (Aldemir, 2007); endoparasites such as *Taenia* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus*, *Ancylostomacanthum*, *Toxocara canis*, *Dipylidium caninum* and *Isospora* spp. (Anosike, 2004; Davoust, 2008; Swai, 2010) and haemo parasites such as *Babesia* spp., *Hepatozoan canis*, and *Dirofilarias* spp. (Beugnet, 1998).

1.3 Aim and Objectives

1.4.1 Aim

The aim of this research is to determine the prevalence of ecto and endoparasites associated with dogs brought for treatment at zonal Veterinary Clinic Kofar Kwaya Katsina state.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

To determine the prevalence of ecto and endoparasites of dogs kept within and around Katsina

To relate the prevalence to sex, ages and species of the dogs.

To identify the common species of parasites afflicting the animals in the area.

1.4 Scope and Limitation

This research was limited to zonal Veterinary Clinic Kofar Kwaya Katsina state and will consider only Dogs among the animals being admitted into that hospital for some specific period of time.

1.5 Research Hypothesis

1. H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex of the species of the dogs.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex of the species of the dogs.

2. H_0 : There is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the ages of the species of the dogs.

H_1 : There is a significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the ages of the species of the dogs.

1.6. Significance of the Study

At the completion of this research, the findings will help the hospital to know which among the ecto or endoparasites was mostly affecting the dogs admitted. It will also serve as a review to the researchers interested in the area of study. The result will also serve as an indicator of the prevalence of the disease found rare within the study area.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Parasites in dogs take many forms, but they all have one thing in common: sooner or later their presence will almost always have an impact on your pet's health or comfort. They can cause anything from mild irritation to serious illness. To cover all of the parasites in detail would (and does) take up a book. So here is an overview of the most common parasites, how they work, and the problems they may cause (AVMA 2015);

First, let's define what a parasite is "A parasite is an organism that lives on or in a host organism and gets its food from or at the expense of its host." According to the Companion Animal Parasite Council (CAPC), many dogs will be infected with parasites at some point in their life.

2.2 Types of Dog Parasites

2.2.1 Internal Dog Parasites

Heartworms enter a dog's bloodstream from the bite of an infected mosquito. The worms mature in the dog's heart (they can grow up to an amazing one foot in length), and clog it. Inflammation in the dog's arterial wall disrupts blood flow, making the heart have to work harder. Once blood flow slows sufficiently, a heartworm-infested dog develops a mild, persistent cough, may become fatigued after only mild exercise, and suffers from a reduced appetite. The end result can be heart failure (AVMA 2015).

Though veterinarians look for these typical signs, most dogs harbouring this parasite do not have clinical symptoms prior to the worms being detected via screening tests. These tests are usually

done during routine veterinary check-ups. The test is so sensitive that it can detect a single worm in a dog's body. However, it can only detect the presence of adult heartworms, so timing is very important. There are other tests to determine the presence of heartworms, and your vet can walk you through them (AVMA 2015).

Three simultaneous factors are necessary for heartworm to become a threat to your dog:

1. other infested dogs
2. mosquitoes to carry the parasite
3. the right temperature

Treatment for heartworm is expensive and hard on the dog and must be administered by a veterinarian. In rare cases, surgery will be required to remove them. Luckily, there are many effective options for heartworm prevention. These include daily and monthly tablets and chewable, and monthly topical.

Note that Collies and certain other herding breeds have a sensitivity to heartworm preventives that is genetically- based, and which your vet can test for.

Intestinal Dog Parasites

Hookworms live inside a dog's digestive system and are acquired either by puppies from their mother (when nursing) or by adult dogs swallowing the parasite's eggs, or having the hookworm burrow into the skin. Hookworm larvae live in soil and can be ingested when the dog comes in contact via eating them or through routine self-cleaning. After attaching to the lining of the intestinal wall, the hookworm feeds on the dog's blood. The resulting blood loss can have serious

effects, especially on puppies. Your veterinarian can detect hookworms by examining a stool sample under a microscope. Infection can be prevented by keeping your dog's environment clean (AVMA 2015).

As with a number of intestinal parasites in dogs, diarrhoea and weight loss are common symptoms of infection.

Ringworm is actually a fungus, not a worm. Because of their still-developing immune system, puppies less than a year old are more susceptible to ringworm. Adult dogs who are malnourished or stressed, or whose immune system is diminished, are also at risk, and the ringworm fungus is easily transmitted. An infected dog will develop lesions on his head, ears, paws, and forelimbs. The lesions cause circular bald spots which sometimes look red in the centre. In mild cases, a dog might suffer only a few broken hairs. In severe cases, the infection can spread over most of the dog's body (AVMA 2015).

Treatment depends on the severity of the infection. Veterinarians typically prescribe a medicated shampoo or ointment to kill the fungus in mild cases. Severe cases may need oral medications, in addition to clipping the fur (AVMA 2015).

Roundworms are an extremely common parasite, and again, puppies are most at risk. They look like white, firm, rounded strips of spaghetti, one to three inches long. Your veterinarian will look for signs of roundworms in the stool sample. Some of the symptoms of roundworm are coughing, vomiting, diarrhoea, or malnourishment. Roundworms can infect other dogs and children (AVMA 2015).

Tapeworms are ingested by your dog, via a host that is harbouring a tapeworm egg. This is usually an adult flea. It will cause your dog to lose weight and have occasional diarrhoea. You'll know if your dog's got them because you'll see segments of the worms around his anus or in his stool. The segments look like grains of rice. Your veterinarian will administer medication by injection or orally. The medication is highly effective. The best protection against tapeworms is to keep your dog free of fleas and away from dead animals and garbage (AVMA 2015).

Whipworms are acquired by licking or sniffing contaminated ground. An adult whipworm is only about 1/3-inch long and resembles a very small piece of thread. They live in the dog's large intestine, but unlike other parasitic worms, they are very difficult to spot in a stool sample. A telltale sign, though, is a stool that has a mucous covering, usually at the tip. Weight loss is the chief symptom of a whipworm infestation. Though whipworms are rarely a cause of death and afflicted dogs will need to be treated with a dewormer (AVMA 2015).

Coccidian, Giardia, and Spirochetes are invasive, non-worm parasites that live in a dog's intestinal tract. What makes them particularly dangerous is that they can infect a dog before he actually appears sick. It may not be clear that the dog is carrying these parasites until stress or another immunity-compromising factor arises. Coccidia are single-celled and found more frequently in puppies, where they may acquire it through their litter mates or mother. Older dogs and cats may also be susceptible. Spirochetes can live in the bloodstream, as well as in the intestine, and can cause Lyme disease, syphilis, and other serious diseases. Giardia are found throughout the U.S. and are, unfortunately, a pervasive protozoa. Transmission of these parasites can come from infected soil, water, faeces, food, other animals, and more. As with all parasites, diligent sanitation practices are important to stave off these parasites (AVMA 2015).

2.2.2 External Dog Parasites

Fleas are tiny wingless insects that feed on mammals, including dogs. Fleabites make some dogs so miserable that they bite and scratch themselves raw. Other dogs do not seem to respond to fleabites with the same intensity. If you see evidence of fleas on your dog, it is essential to get rid of them as quickly as possible, before the population grows. Hungry fleas sometimes bite humans too, leaving small, red, itchy bumps most commonly observed on the wrists and ankles.

You may be able to see the dark fleas, about the size of sesame seeds, scurrying around on the skin. Their favourite spots include the base of the ears and the rump. Look closely to sparsely haired places, like the groin, for telltale signs. A more accurate way to diagnose fleas, however, when live ones aren't observed, is to part the fur in several places and look for tiny black specks about the size of poppy seeds. These specks are flea faeces, composed of digested blood. If you're not sure whether you're looking at "flea dirt" or just plain dirt, place it on a damp piece of white tissue. After a minute or so, a small red spot or halo will become apparent if it's flea faeces since the blood re-hydrates and diffuses into the tissue (AVMA 2015).

Ticks can cause a number of serious illnesses, and canine tick-borne diseases include Lyme disease, Ehrlichiosis, and Rocky Mountain Spotted Fever. There are over 800 species of ticks worldwide and they all feed on the blood of mammals, birds, and reptiles. Ticks go through four life stages. Given the many ailments associated with ticks, annual screening by your vet for tick disease is mandatory. There are broad-spectrum antibiotics that are effective for tick-borne diseases.

Check your dog for ticks daily if he spends any time outside, and whenever you see one, take it off immediately. The best way to do this is to numb the tick with rubbing alcohol or petroleum jelly,

then pull it off with tweezers. Once removed, kill the tick by putting it in a container of alcohol. Prevent an infestation by treating your dog with a medication, dip, spray, or powder as recommended by your veterinarian (AVMA 2015).

Lice and mites are microscopic organisms that feed on your dog's skin and cause itching, hair loss, and infection. Generally speaking, lice and mites are two different species, but they function and behave in a very similar way. Lice live in a dog's hair and can be killed with an insecticide used for ticks or fleas. Various kinds of mites inhabit different areas of the dog, and the problems they cause are generally known as mange. Demodectic mange causes hair loss around the forehead, eyes, muzzle, and forepaws. Note that dog lice and human lice are different species—dog lice need dog blood and human lice need human blood. While humans may occasionally be bitten by dog lice, they will not get an infestation. Your dog may have mites if he shakes his head and scratches his ears. Scabies, which affects humans as well as dogs, is caused when mites burrow into the dog's skin. Scabies usually affects the ears, elbows, legs, and face. There is also a mite that causes “walking dandruff” on a dog's head, back, and neck. This mite also causes itchy red spots on humans. All mites should be diagnosed by a skin scraping by a veterinarian (AVMA 2015).

2.3 How to Prevent Dog Parasites

To avoid parasite problems before they start, think of these three “M”s (AVMA 2015):

1. **Medicate** with preventives. Yes, there are effective treatment options for once your dog is infested—some are simple and others more complicated. But with the wide availability of extremely effective preventive medications, you can help ensure that your buddy is not plagued with squirming, burrowing, or biting pests. For internal, intestinal, and external

parasite preventives, ask your vet for her recommendations for the particular needs of your dog.

2. **Monitor** your pet with annual screening tests from your veterinarian. You should also watch for changes in your dog. If he is behaving differently, or there are changes in his appetite or how much water he is drinking, these may alert you to a potential problem.
3. **Maintain** a clean environment for your dog. Make sure bedding, food and water dishes, coats, etc., are cleaned regularly. Keep him away from garbage, dead animals, and other dogs or cats who may be infected. Remove faeces at least once a week from wherever your dog eliminates.

2.4 Can Dog Parasites Be Transmitted to Humans?

Intestinal parasites in dogs do indeed pose a health risk to people. According to PetMD, children are at most serious risk, especially if play behaviour is in an environment where dog, cat, or raccoon faeces may be present, such as in a sandbox. This is another reason thorough sanitary precautions should be taken.

Of course, people are also routinely subjected to a case of fleas, ticks, lice, and mites, which easily pass between species.

Note: This article is designed to help inform you about parasites in dogs and is not meant to take the place of a veterinary diagnosis or consultation. If you think your dog might have a parasite, contact your vet right away to set up an appointment for an examination and to ensure that your dog receives the safest and most effective treatment.

Sources: American Veterinary Medical Association (AVMA); Companion Animal Parasite Council (CAPC); Heartworm Society; Merck Veterinary Manual; Pet Education; PetMD

2.5 Biological Control of Endoparasites

The principle of this strategy bases on the rule that all species of animals are regulated by other living organisms to prevent the uncontrolled increase of one population (Grønvold *et al.*, 1996). In the context of parasite control, it usually means the use of a naturally occurring antagonist to lower a pest population which would otherwise cause losses to animal production. Grønvold *et al.* (1996) conclude that of all possible antagonistic organisms only nematophagous fungi, earthworms and dung beetles have realistic potential as biological control agents, although there are several species that little or nothing is known about and therefore their potential use for biological control cannot be assessed/estimated.

2.5.1 Earthworms

Earthworms are soil inhabitants that live on organic matter deposited on the soil surface. Organic matter gets pulled down below the surface either for food or to plug the earthworms burrows. Therefore the major contribution of earthworms towards the biological control of nematodes is seen in the destruction of eggs and larvae by digesting them or transferring them to deeper levels of the soil where chances that they can reach the surface as infective larvae are very low (Persson, 1974 in Grønvold *et al.*, 1996). A New Zealand study examined the ability of mixed earthworm populations, alone or in combination with other biological control organisms to reduce pasture infectivity in two experiments (spring and autumn) (Waghorn *et al.*, 2002). “Earthworms reduced the total number of larvae recovered in both trials and the number recovered from herbage in trial

1.”

2.5.2 Dung Beetles

The term ‘dung beetle’ refers to those beetles that live partly or exclusively on the dung of herbivorous; most species belong to the family Scarabaeidae. Adult beetles use the liquid contents of manure for their nourishment and some species form dung balls which they bury and lay their eggs in, others just live in the manure pats (Thomas, 2001). The activity of dung beetles is being discussed controversially: by breaking up the pats and partially burying the manure, they enhance the drying up of the dung which deteriorates growing conditions for larvae (Grønvold *et al.*, 1996) but by the same activities in bad weather conditions they might help the larvae to survive by airing out the pats and thereby providing oxygen to the larvae.

Bryan (1973/1976) was able to show in his experiments with manure pats and dung beetles that dung beetles can reduce larvae on herbage in between 40 to 93%, the percentage of reduction correlated positively with the number of beetles. Bryan also found out that the burial of dung containing larvae contributed to their longevity and he concluded that the burial can create a favourable environment for larval development because they are protected from extreme climatic conditions (Bryan, 1973 and 1976). Waghorn *et al.* (2002) also confirmed the influence of dung burial in respect to larval development with the result of significantly more larval recoveries than when dung was not buried, although dung was manually buried in order to mimic the natural activities of the dung beetle. Vlassoff *et al.* (2001) also mention that results of studies with dung beetles have been variable, some species reduce and others increase larval numbers (Fincher, 1973).

2.5.3 Nematophagous Fungi

In this special case, it means the use of the naturally occurring nematophagous or nematode-destroying fungi to control parasitic nematodes in ruminants. Nematophagous fungi are soil inhabitants and can be found in most soil types throughout the world. Research has shown they are found more frequently in organic production systems than any other (Jansson *et al.*, 2004).

The fungi can be divided into groups depending on their mode of affecting nematodes: there are nematode trapping, endoparasitic, egg and female parasitic and toxin producing fungi (Jansson *et al.*, 1997). The fungi of the nematode trapping group all have in common that they form a vegetative hyphal system that produces trapping organs such as sticky nets, knobs or rings (Hertzberg *et al.*, 2002). When for example a nematode gets trapped, the fungi penetrate the nematode cuticle with their hyphae that then grow out and fill the body of the nematode to finally digest it (Grønvold *et al.*, 1996).

The idea of using nematophagous fungi to control parasitic nematodes is based on the reduction of the larval level in the faeces before larvae reach the vegetation, which requires a high density of spores in the faeces. There are two possible ways to reach that high spore density, the first is to artificially inoculate the faeces and the second way is to administer the spores orally. Since the first way seems not viable the only possibility was to discover those fungi that are able to survive the gastro-intestinal tract of ruminants. This complex problem may have been one reason for the rather slow progress of science concerning this topic. Research had started as early as in the 1940s but with little success at the time (Hertzberg *et al.*, 2002). In the 1960s there was evidence found for predaceous fungi working against

parasitic nematodes (Parnell and Gordon, 1963), but these experiments were not continued. The major breakthrough was achieved at the beginning of the 1990s when Larsen et al. (1991) selected fungi that were able to survive in vitro conditions simulating the passage through the gastro-intestinal tract of cattle. The two genera tested, *Arthrobotrys* and *Duddingtonia*, both showed the ability for survival with the genus *Duddingtonia* performing significantly better, 87.5% versus 46% (Larsen et al., 1991). These results were the final trigger for detailed research in this area and since then many trials have been undertaken in several countries in which faecal samples of sheep have been screened for predacious fungi (Larsen et al., 1994; Hay et al., 1997; Ghahfarokhi et al., 2004). Even after the promising results of the feeding trials with *Duddingtonia* flagrans (Wolstrup et al., 1994; Githigia et al., 1997; Faedo et al., 1998) science continued to research a wider range of fungi until the end of the 1990's when trials with fungi other than *Duddingtonia* flagrans started to decrease. From the year 2000 onwards most scientists started to focus on the potential of *D. flagrans*. One of the first questions that occurred in that context was whether or not *D. flagrans* had the ability to grow beyond faeces into the surrounding soil and by doing so it could control emerging third stage larvae from eggs deposited prior or post deposition of fungal spores (Faedo et al., 2000). The results confirmed that *D. flagrans* significantly reduces the number of infective larvae that migrate onto the pasture and it also showed that there was no effect on larval migration of prior and post deposited faeces. In the first years, most of in vivo trials focused on the potential of larval reduction by the fungus and either there was little knowledge about the amount of chlamydospores necessary for a successful reduction nor it was clear if the larvae of different species would be affected in the same way. After the excretion of the spores the faeces get colonized by the *Duddingtonia* mycel.

Excretion density of the spores and growth rate of the mycel correlates positively (Hertzberg *et al.*, 2002). *D. flagrans* is a fungus that produces trapping nets and the presence of any nematodes induces the trap production, which lasts for approx. 2-3 weeks (Gronvold *et al.*, 1996). The optimum temperature for the development of trapping nets is 30°C; a rise in temperature to 35°C or more causes any fungus activity to stop and a fall in temperature to below 10°C reduces the trapping ability (Gronvold *et al.*, 1996). The trials used spore numbers in between 3×10^5 and 5×10^7 chlamyospores per day, some dosed it per kilogram bodyweight (Githigia *et al.*, 1997; Larsen *et al.*, 1998; Faedo *et al.*, 2000), and others administered a set dose per sheep per day (Faedo *et al.*, 1998; Knox and Faedo, 2001; Waller *et al.*, 2001ab). Dose trials from Pêna *et al.* in 2002 showed that there was no significant difference in a dose between 1×10^5 and 1×10^6 spores/ kg BodyWeight (BW)/ day, with every dose above 1×10^4 successfully reducing the larval development by more than 90%. Chandrawathani *et al.* 2003 experimented with 1.25, 2.5 and 5×10^5 spores/ kg liveweight / day and found that a reduction >99% of larval recovery was only achieved with 2.5×10^5 or more. For a successful application of the fungus treatment, a feasible way of administration should be integrated into the everyday farming routine. Most studies in the last years administered the spores within a daily supplement ration (Fontenot *et al.*, 2003; Chandrawathani *et al.*, 2004; Waller *et al.*, 2004) although Waller *et al.* had investigated the potential ways of administration in 2 studies in 2001. These studies showed that feedback formulations and a 'fungal controlled release device' (CRD's) could have some potential but no further investigation has been conducted since then.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Description of Study Area

Katsina veterinary clinic was established during the former Katsina state administration in the year 1974 and was transferred to its permanent site of Katsina veterinary services department under the ministry of agriculture and natural resources. It has the mandate of maintaining the health status of all livestock in Katsina state, safeguarding public health through prevention and control zoonosis, and developing hides and skins activities to ensure foreign exchange earnings for the state at large. The purpose of building the clinic was to take care of sick and injured animals. Activities under this unit are mainly curative and preventive as well as surveillance of diseases.

Veterinary doctors diagnose animal health problems, vaccinate against diseases, medicate animals suffering from infections or illness, treat, dress wounds, set fractures, perform surgery and advise owners about animal feeding behaviour and breeding. Veterinary clinics are dedicated to providing high-quality veterinary care for pets with personal support and advice for their guardians in calm, comfortable and clean surroundings. With respect to this objective, the establishment has strived hard to meet the demands of its customers thus leading to the progress of the experienced establishment in both clinic and home services. They treat animals with the use of medical equipment such as stethoscopes, surgical instruments and diagnostic equipment. The veterinary doctors in the clinic work with food animals or horses usually drive to farms to provide veterinary services for herds or individual animals these veterinarians test for and vaccinate against diseases and consult with farm owners and caretakers regarding animal production, feeding and housing

issues. They also treat and dress wounds, set fractures and perform surgeries including cesarean sessions (cs) on animals that are about to give birth by themselves at home.

3.1.1 Organizational Structure of the Study Area

3.1.1.1. Departmental Functions: The veterinary clinic consists of three departments which are the clinic floor, laboratory and artificial insemination centre.

3.1.1.2. Clinic Floor: The clinic floor is where most of the clinic activities happen which is the examination of patients, diagnoses, treatment, prevention and control for animal diseases. In the examination room, animals receive routine exams and simple treatments and medical staff collect patient history about a patient. An operating room is also located on the clinic floor, it is where major surgical procedures such as fracture repair, hernia surgery, dystocia and cesarean sections.

3.1.1.3. Laboratory: The laboratory is an area located inside a veterinary hospital laboratory equipment is used to analyse patient tests and samples.

Artificial Insemination Center: Artificial insemination is a method of breeding using frozen straws of semen for instance in cattle, artificial insemination is successful when it's done at the proper time of the cow's heat cycle. In the artificial insemination centre, cross-breeding is also done. Crossbreeding is defined as the process or act of providing offspring, particularly through mating two purebred individuals but come from different breeds, varieties or even species.

3.1.2. Organogram

Fig: 1 Organogram of Veterinary Clinic

3.2. Study Design and Population

A cross-sectional study was conducted to assess knowledge, attitudes, and practices and estimate the prevalence of ecto and endo parasites associated with dogs brought for treatment at zonal veterinary clinic. The study population comprised all dogs brought for treatment at zonal veterinary clinic Kofar kwaya Katsina.

3.3. Sample

The data collected was secondary data where the sample size depends on the available information. The variables to be examined were dogs affected by ecto and endo parasite. Data of 40 dogs were taken with their age, sex, species and the type of parasite. From the month of October to December 2021

3.4. Ethical Consideration

Research permission was granted by the Director of the Zonal Veterinary Clinic Kofar Kwaya, Katsina. Participation in the study was voluntary.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

A statistical method is employed in the analysis of the data gathered by the use of simple tables and percentages. The tabulation plays a big role in presenting the information concisely and precisely, thus easy to read, interpret and understand the gathered data. So the data obtained will be summarized into tables where necessary applicable. An inferential statistical technique that was also adopted for this study is chi-square to determine the significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex and age of the species of the dogs. These are elements included in data analysis and Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS V.26) will also be employed.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter contains the descriptive statistics and the analysis of the data collected and the discussion on the results of the analysis.

4.2 Data Presentation

Table 4.1 Distribution of Dogs by Species

		Species		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Local Breed	37	92.5	92.5	92.5
Valid German Breed	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1 shows that 37(92.5%) were local breed while 3(7.5%) were German breed. This shows that majority of dogs brought for treatment at zonal veterinary clinic, Kofar kwaya Katsina were local breed as shown in figure 4.1 below.

Figure 4.1 Bar chart showing the distribution of Dogs by Species.

Table 4.2: Distribution of Dogs by affected Parasites

		Parasites			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Ecto	32	80.0	80.0	80.0
Valid	Endo	8	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

The table 4.2 shows that ecto parasites 32(80%) is more affecting the dogs while endo is affecting the dog 8(20%). This shows that majority of the dogs are being affected by ecto parasite as shown in figure 4.2 below.

Figure 4.2 Bar chart showing

Table 4.3: Distribution of dogs by disease (Both Ecto and Endo)

Disease				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid				
Tick	19	47.5	47.5	47.5
Mange	2	5.0	5.0	52.5
Mites	5	12.5	12.5	65.0
Lice	6	15.0	15.0	80.0
Ancylostomasp	5	12.5	12.5	92.5
p				
Ascarisspp	3	7.5	7.5	100.0
Total	40	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.3 shows that tick 19(47.5%) is more affecting the dogs, then lice 6(15%), Mites and Ancylostomaspp 5(12.5%) ,Ascaris spp 3(7.5%), Mange 2(5%) as shown in figure 4.3 below.

Figure 4.3 Bar chart showing the Distribution of dogs by disease (Both Ecto and Endo)

Table 4.4: Disease and parasites

Disease * Parasites Crosstabulation				
Count				
		Parasites		Total
		Ecto	Endo	
Diseas	Tick	19	0	19
e	Mange	2	0	2

Mites	5	0	5
Lice	6	0	6
Ancylostomas	0	5	5
pp			
Ascarisspp	0	3	3
Total	32	8	40

Table 4.4 shows cross tabulation of the disease and the parasites where tick 19(59.4%) was the major ecto parasite disease affecting the dogs while Ancylostomaspp5(62.5%) was among the major endo parasites disease that affecting the dogs as shown in figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Bar chart showing the distribution of Disease and parasites

Table 4.5 dog specie and parasite

Crosstab

Count

		Parasites		Total
		Ecto	Endo	
Species	Local Breed	29	8	37
	German Breed	3	0	3
Total		32	8	40

Table 4.5 shows cross tabulation of the specie and the parasites where local breed 29(78.4%) were mostly affected by ecto parasite disease as shown in figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5 Bar chart showing the relationship between dog specie and parasite

Table 4.6 chi square test between dog specie and parasite

N	Chi-Square	Alpha	p-value	Decision
40	0.811	0.05	.368	not significant

Table 4.6 Test whether parasite infection depends on the species of the dog. The computed p- value was 0.368 which is greater than the standard p- value 0.05. Therefore the result is not significant.

It is concluded that parasite infection do depend on the specie of the dog.

4.3 Analysis

Hypothesis one

H_01 : There is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex of the species of the dogs.

Table 4.7 Cross tabulation between dog specie and the sex of the dogs affected by disease

Crosstab

Count

		Sex		Total
		Male	Female	
Species	Local Breed	25	12	37
	German Breed	2	1	3
Total		27	13	40

Table 4.7 shows the prevalence of disease per specie based on gender.

Table 4.8 Chi-Square Tests for dog specie and the sex of the dogs

N	Chi-Square	Alpha	p-value	Decision
40	0.01	0.05	.974	not significant

Table 4.8 Test whether sex depends on the species of the dog. The computed p- value was 0.974 which is greater than the standard p- value 0.05. Therefore the result is not significant. It is concluded that sex does not depend on the specie of the dog. We retain the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex of the species of the dogs.

Hypothesis two

H_02 : There is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the ages of the species of the dogs.

Table 4.9 Dogs’ specie and their corresponding ages

Crosstab

Count

		Age		Total
		<1year (Puppy)	>=1year (Adult)	
Species	Local Breed	10	27	37
	German Breed	1	2	3
Total		11	29	40

Table 4.9 shows that adult local breed were mostly affected by the disease followed by puppy.

Table 4.10 chi square test for dogs' specie and their corresponding ages

N	Chi-Square	Alpha	p-value	Decision
40	0.055	0.05	.814	not significant

Table 4.6 Test whether age depends on the species of the dog. The computed p- value was 0.814 which is greater than the standard p – value 0.05. Therefore the result is not significant. We retain the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the ages of the species of the dogs.

Table 4.11 dogs' specie and the type of disease

Species * Disease Crosstabulation								
Count								
		Disease						Total
		Tick	Mang e	Mites	Lice	Ancylosto maspp	Ascariss pp	
Species	Local	16	2	5	6	5	3	37
	Breed							
	German	3	0	0	0	0	0	3
	Breed							
Total		19	2	5	6	5	3	40

Table 4.12 displays the cross tabulation of the dogs specie and the type of disease. The result shows that tick that belongs to ecto parasite is more affecting local breed.

4.4 Answers to the research hypothesis

H_01 : There is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex of the species of the dogs.

From the results of the analysis conducted, we retain the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis that is there is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex of the species of the dogs.

H_12 : There is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the ages of the species of the dogs.

The results shows that the null hypothesis was retain that is there is no significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the ages of the species of the dogs.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Discussion

This research aimed to determine the prevalence of ecto and endo parasites of dogs, the prevalence to sex, ages and species of the dogs brought for treatment in the zonal Veterinary Clinic Kofar Kwaya Katsina state.

Knowledge, attitudes, and practices were assessed and the prevalence of ecto parasites and endo parasite associated with dogs brought for treatment at zonal veterinary clinic was estimated. 40 dogs was taken with their age, sex specie type and the type of disease. Simple tables and percentages were used to present the data while inferential statistical technique was adopted where chi square was used for this study is to determine the significant relationship between the prevalence of the disease and the sex and age of the species of the dogs. The data presented shows that 37(92.5%) were local breed while 3(7.5%) were German breed and ecto parasites disease 32(80%) is more affecting the dogs than the endo parasite 8(20%).

Among the disease affecting the dogs, tick 19(47.5%) is more affecting them followed by lice 6(15%) and little from Mites and Ancylostomaspp, Ascarisspp and Mange. Among the parasites affecting the dogs, tick 19(59.4%) was the major ecto parasite disease affecting the dogs while Ancylostomaspp 5(62.5%) was among the major endo parasites disease that affecting the dogs.

The result of the hypothesis in an attempt to test whether parasite infection depends on the species of the dog was not significant that is parasite infection do depend on the specie of the dog. Secondly hypothesis testing whether sex depends on the species of the dog was not significant that is sex does not depend on the specie of the dog. Hypothesis testing whether age depends on the species

of the dog was rejected that is there was no significant difference in the prevalence rates of ecto, endo parasites and based on sex of dogs in the present study.

5.2 Conclusion

The findings resulted to the following conclusions:

1. Majority of dogs brought for treatment at zonal veterinary clinic, Kofar kwaya Katsina were local breed.
2. Most of the dogs brought for treatment were being affected by ecto parasite and the tick is more affecting them.
3. Tick was the major ecto parasite disease affecting the dogs while *Ancylostomaspp* was among the major endo parasites disease that affecting the dogs brought for treatment.
4. Parasite infection does depend on the specie of the dog.
5. Parasite infection does depend on the specie of the dog.
6. Sex does not depend on the specie of the dog

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. There is also the current lack of verified information on the dogs with serious disease. For these reasons dog owners should be reporting any disease they noticed from their dogs.
2. Affected dogs need to be separated from unaffected ones to avoid being contacted with communicable disease.
3. There is the need for health education to dog breeders and owners, vaccination of all stray dogs and proper use at least of acaricides and routine vermifuges.

4. The emphasis should be put on alternative strategies for prevention because this measure aligns more with the overall principles of veterinary clinics, which is to maintain health rather than curing disease
5. Future research in this area seems promising, there remain a lot of dogs to be studied but it is possible that there are some dogs that possess some disease that has a great side-effects.

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Appendix

Introductory Letter for research signed by Supervisor Malam Abdullahi Shehu Ado and the Director of the zonal veterinary Clinic Kofar Kwaya katsina.

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College of Natural and Applied Sciences
Department of Biological Sciences
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Date..18-10-21....

The Director,
Katsina Veterinary Zonal
Office, KATSINA STATE

Dear Sir/Madam

REQUEST FOR PROJECT ASSISTANCE

The bearer.....ZANIRA IMAM..... with registration number NAS/BIO/17/3137
is a 400 level student of this department, currently writing a project research which is a partial fulfillment for the award of bachelor degree in biology. We are therefore soliciting your permission to give the student access to materials needed to accomplish the task.

Thanks

With regards,

Supervisor/Project coordinator:
Sign: 18th Oct. 2021
Date:

T/c clinic
Pls attend accordingly
